

crosses and their controls in inducing and differentiating calli (Table 2).

Using early sowing and short-day treatments, the parent plants headed 80 d sooner than those grown under conventional cultivation. It only took 10 mo for the entire anther culture process, from cultivating the parents to growing enough anther lines for transplanting. The improved procedure took 1 yr less than the anther culture technique routinely used in rice breeding. ■

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Table 2. Comparison of anther culture ability of five F₁ crosses. Shandong, China. 1993/94.

Cross	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%) ^a	Calli plated (no.)	Green plantlets regenerated (%) ^b
<i>Treatment 1^c</i>				
89-7013/Kinuhikari	391	36.57	240	8.33
89-7013/Yamauta	385	30.58	256	51.79
89-7013/Xiangqueno	407	38.56	247	28.67
Akenohoshi/Xiangqueno	416	56.49	243	36.21
Akenohoshi/Yakomagokari	395	42.87	255	34.05
Total	1994	41.01	1241	31.81
<i>Treatment 2^d</i>				
89-7013/Kinuhikari	400	34.50	250	11.60
89-7013/Yamauta	400	33.50	250	50.40
89-7013/Xiangqueno	400	40.25	250	26.40
Akenohoshi/Xiangqueno	400	52.50	250	38.40
Akenohoshi/Yakomagokari	400	46.25	250	32.80
Total	2000	41.40	1250	31.92
^a Anthers producing calli Total anthers plated × 100.		^b Calli producing green plantlets Total calli plated × 100.		^c Crosses made in June 1994.
				^d Check; crosses made in 1993.

Expression of an engineered cysteine proteinase inhibitor (Oryzacystatin-186) in transgenic rice plants

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Meloidogyne spp. (root knot nematodes) damage upland rice in both Asia and Africa. Their wide host range ensures other crops in rotation with rice are at risk in both upland and intermittently flooded, lowland rice.

Hirschmanniella spp. (rice root knot nematodes) also damage lowland rice but only when cropping is intensive. *Pratylenchus* spp. (root lesion nematodes) occur in virtually all Asian and many African upland rice crops and can cause up to 50% yield loss. Our goal is to provide a basis for concomitant control of all nematode pests of rice.

Efficient tissue culture, regeneration, DNA delivery, and selection methodologies have been established for elite African (ITA212, IDSA6, LAC23,

WAB56-104) and Asian (IR64) genotypes.

The plasmids pWRG4517(Δ86 (CaMV 35S-promoter~oc-IΔ86~NOS-polyA) + CaMV35S~ promoter-*aphIV* ~ S-poly A) and pWRG2920 (*ubi-5'* region ~ *uida* ~ NOS-polyA) were constructed and used for stable transformation of rice. The *oc-IΔ86* gene was designed by protein engineering to improve the efficacy of native rice *oc-I* against nematodes (Urwin et al 1995). *Oc-IΔ86* differs from *Oc-I* by only one amino acid (Asp86 deleted, Urwin et al 1995). Particle gun bombardment, selection, and regeneration of transformed plants were carried out as previously described (Christou et al 1991). Two days after particle bombardment, the explants were transferred to a medium containing hygromycin to minimize the establishment of chimeric calli (a mix of transformed and non-transformed tissues, Christou and Ford 1995). Twelve days after bombardment, the immature embryos exhibited necrotic areas and large proliferations of embryogenic calli from the scutellum. Embryogenic tissue was repeatedly selected at each subculture. After 3-6 wk, we observed clear differential growth between transformed (*hyg+*) and nontransformed (*hyg-*) calli during

proliferation, regeneration, and germination. Transformation of the *hyg+* clones was further confirmed by GUS, PCR, Southern blot, and Western blot analyses of regenerated plants. Transformation frequencies were 1-6% from the elite African and Asian genotypes tested (av: ITA212, 2.6%; LAC23, 1.8%; WAB56-104, 1.1%; IDSA6, 1.8%; and IR64, 1.1%). More than 80 independent transformed lines have been obtained to date.

When both pWRG4517Δ86 and pWRG2920 were used for transformation, *hyg+* clones and regenerated plants became intensely blue after GUS histochemical staining. In some cases, transformed GUS-negative plants were regenerated from *hyg+* clones. When only pWRG4517Δ86 was used, the regenerated plants were first screened by PCR using two primers (AAGAAGACGTTCCAACCACG and GATCTCCAATCTGCGGGATC), amplifying a 1.4-kb fragment containing the *aphIV* gene. Southern blot analysis confirmed the integration of the pWRG4517Δ86 plasmid in the rice genomic DNA (Fig. 1). Levels of oryzacystatin (*Oc-IΔ86*) in plant roots were detected in four of nine transformed rice lines by Western blot analysis (Fig. 2).

1. Southern analysis of one ITA212 hygromycin-resistant callus line (C) and regenerated plant (P). DNA was either undigested (UD) or digested by *Not1*, *Sac1*, or *Kpn1*. The *Not1* sites are flanking the 2-kb *CaMV35S*-promoter-*aphIV*-NOS-poly A sequence in pWRG4517Δ86 plasmid and only one *Sac1* site is present in this plasmid. Nontransformed (NT) and previously obtained transformed (T) rice plants (Christou et al 1991) were used as negative and positive controls, respectively. The membrane was hybridized with the *aphIV* gene.

2. Western blot of an SDS PAGE gel probed with a polyclonal antibody raised to oryzacystatin Oc-I (Urwin et al 1995). Lanes 1-3 were loaded with 2 µg total protein from ITA212-transformed rice plants regenerated from three independent lines. Lanes 4-8 were loaded with 2 µg total protein from an ITA212-untransformed rice plant to which 0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, or 1% Oc-I protein was added.

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An improved biolistic method for transformation and production of fertile transgenic Pusa Basmati rice plants

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An improved biolistic procedure for the transformation of embryogenic suspension cells of Pusa Basmati 1 (aromatic, fine grained, semidwarf plant type, Group 1 indica), has been developed. The procedure involves using of suitable reporter or other useful genes, osmotic preconditioning of cells on a medium supplemented with 0.25 M mannitol prior to bombardment, gold particles for DNA delivery, and plant regeneration medium with high agarose concentration (1.0%). This procedure allowed us to produce more than 600 transient transformants and 12-50 fertile transgenic plants per bombarded filter carrying 0.5 mL settled cell volume (scv) of rice cells.

We have been working on biolistic transformation of Basmati rice (Pusa Basmati 1) using gene constructs that can potentially improve the defense against insect attack and water stress tolerance. Pusa Basmati 1 is an improved, fine grain, aromatic, and semidwarf indica rice variety that essentially belongs to Varietal Group 1 (Jain et al 1995). Plasmids carrying β-

glucuronidase (GUS) gene or other agronomically important genes driven by the actin 1 gene promoter (*Act1*), were constructed for rice transformation. Act1F-GUS plasmid (McElroy et al 1990) was used for transient gene expression studies; other plasmids carrying potato protease inhibitor 2 (*PIN2*) gene, or a late embryogenesis-abundant protein (*Lea3*) gene from barley (see figure), were used for optimization of the biolistic process and production of useful transgenic plants. The structure of these plasmids is shown in the figure.

In the beginning, we used the biolistic japonica rice transformation procedure developed in this laboratory (Cao et al 1992) for DNA delivery into Pusa Basmati 1 cells. The procedure involved bombardment of M10 tungsten particles coated with plasmid DNA using the DuPont Helium PDS-1000 device keeping the bombardment pressure of 1500 psi, gap distance (distance between the rupture disc and the launch point of macroprojectile) of 1.0 cm, and target cell distance (distance between the target cells and the launch point of the microprojectiles) of 12 cm. Each filter, carrying 0.5 mL scv of suspension cells, was bombarded twice with tungsten particles coated with 2.5 µg plasmid DNA. This procedure produced per filter paper an average of 24 blue spots (transient transformants, see table, line 1) or 4.0-6.8 ammonium glufosinate-resistant (AG^R) calli (see table, lines 6 and 12). For practical plant genetic transformation work, at least several hundred potentially generated cells